

UBD | **SBE**

University of Brunei Darussalam
BB-2208 Human Resource Management
Ideal Multifield Farm – The Warwick Model
Dk. Syahirunnisaa Sahira Pg Shahminan (17B8108)

Abstract

The goal of this report is to focus on the potential of how The Warwick Model could be used to improve the management and yields of a local agricultural company, Ideal Multifeed farm company. This report will start with providing a general introduction regarding the topic. It will then outline and discuss the problem statement by looking at the case analysis and five elements of the model. Finally, the paper concludes with a few alternative solutions and recommendation based on the model.

Introduction

1. Warwick Model

This Warwick model was developed by Hendry and Pettigrew at center for strategy and change, University of Warwick around the year 1990s. This model highlights on analytical resource management and the impact of the role of HR function on HR Strategy content. The model mainly concentrated on charting the context, distinguishing the organizational (inner) context and environmental (outer) context and their influences of HRM. We will use this model to assist in improving problem of Ideal Multifeed Farm Company.

2. Company Background

Ideal Multifeed Farm Company was found by the Late Pehin Orang Kaya Di-Gadong Seri Diraja Laila Utama Haji Awang Abdul Rahman in the year 1969. The farm company since then, has been producing and supplying Halal poultry meat and eggs to not just restaurants, but supermarket as well. The company now is managed by the founder's son, Haji Awang Ahmand Morsidi. On a daily basis, the farm company butchered around 200 chickens, produced around 40,000 eggs monthly. As for now, the numbers increased up to 110,000 eggs and 7,700 of slaughtered chickens every day.

As he mentioned, Hj Awg Ahmad Morshidi, he believes the most important thing for your company to be success, one needs to know their way around and it is also subject to management skills. In addition, he stated that it is essential for employers to provide a healthy work environment for the employee; to be friendly yet professional. As this will impact the overall production and performance.

The productivity level all depend on their company's management. For Ideal Multifeed farm themselves, they implement the daily report method to make sure that the management of the company achieves efficient, excellent and consistent work. This also would result in quick identification of problems, and hence, enables for a quick response or solution.

Problem Statement

The challenges faced by the Ideal Multifeed Company, as mentioned by the managing director of the company, includes meeting the increase in number of competitors. He also mentioned, the high demand of the people and then unable to meet the needs. But they have developed good relationships with their clients. With that loyalty. The clients are willing to return back in supporting their business. Looking at the Warwick Model, we would figure out how to tackle the problems mentioned above. Having that said, the next section would be focusing on how to tackle those above problem.

Case Analysis

As stated above, Ideal Multifeed is facing a few challenges that mainly involves the production. In this section, we will try to solve the challenges and refer to the Warwick model. Ideally, we first need to understand the elements of Warwick Model before implementing it. The Warwick Model consists of 5 elements;

1. *The outer context*: political, technical, and competitive factors, among others
2. *The inner context* : the structure, leadership, culture, task-technology
3. *Business strategy content*: objectives, product market, and general strategy
4. *HRM context*: role, definition, organisation, HR outputs
5. *HRM content*: HR flow, reward systems, employee relations, work systems, and other aspects.

Alternative Solutions and recommendations

Below are some recommendations and solutions to make to improve the production in companies such as ideal Multifeed farm:

- Participation in agricultural training and extension program. This method has statistically and positively brought significant impact in the total and value of production. Advancing the skills and training the workers is the key solution. This was proven during the building of Canada's agricultural labour force.
- Raising awareness about regarding the opportunities in agriculture as to attract more workers pursuing the industry.
- The development of reward system (incentives) as regularly mentioned in the topic of Human Resource management, this could motivate, retain and motivate not only workers but people outside the company. These rewards and promotional opportunities could be done in several ways:
 - 1) Rewarding Superior performance: Extension organizations have to develop a reward system which encourages superior performance so that pay and wage administration will be an effective tool to promote performance, motivation, and satisfaction. A clear job description, performance standards, and performance appraisal will help in evaluating extension work and rewarding people for meritorious service.
 - 2) Improved Working Conditions at the Field Level: The reward system must also be internally equitable. The relative importance of field-level extension functionaries has to be realized in terms of pay compensation and other amenities.
- The capability of responding to changes in relation to its environment. In other words, companies have to cope with changes in farm technology, needs of farms, market economy, communication methods, etc. for instance. This organizational development allows for planned changes in the organization's tasks, techniques, structure, and people. Attitudes, values, and practices of the organization are changed so that it can

manage with changing conditions. The employees also gain greater skills such as to deal with new problems.

The earlier procedure to human resource development emphasized individual development with training and proper supervision. The need for improving the quality of work life through making the job more satisfying and productive has been greatly felt. Factors such as the nature of the job or the role or incentives and rewards and involvement of employees in work decisions are important for improving the overall management

Conclusion

The important aspect factor in the success of organizations is bettering their human resources. The proper planning and implementation of the human resource system will result in overall effectiveness. The Warwick Model could potentially be one of the effective approach to tackle challenges as above, however, it is important to note that the prime solution is to first recognize what is lacking in the company itself.

References:

Musa, S. F. P. D. H., Pg Hj Idris, P. S. R., & Basir, K. H. (2020). *Inspiring Agripreneurs of Brunei*. UNISSA Press, Universiti Islam Sultan Sharif Ali.

Government of Canada's Sector Council Program. (n.d, 2011). Stenghtening Human Resources In Agriculture. [silo.tips_strengthening-human-resources-in-agriculture.pdf](#)